

Title: Cyber Diplomacy in the United States and Estonia

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ABSTRACT

As nations evolve technologically, their governments have begun to increasingly rely on cyber diplomacy to combat cyberspace threats. As a result, it is imperative for governments to improve their methods and strategies. This paper examines the landscape of cyber diplomacy with a comparative analysis of the United States and Estonia to determine the areas of improvement for the United States. Estonia is a good example to compare the approach of the United States due to its innovative institutions, rooted in lessons from the 2007 cyber-attacks. While the United States has made legislative and organizational strides, such as through the Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021 and the creation of the Bureau of Cyberspace and Digital Policy, the United States is over reliant on international partnerships, underutilizing domestic actors. On the other hand, Estonia uses a whole-of-country model, incorporating government, private sector, and civilian actors. Because Estonia does this, the country can incorporate a variety of perspectives when it comes to making decisions. To achieve this whole-of-country approach, the United States should attempt to employ people from different backgrounds for the Bureau of Cyberspace and Digital Policy, and the bureau should create goals that call for a whole-of-country approach.

KEYWORDS: Bureau of Cyberspace and Digital Policy (CDP), cyber diplomacy, Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021, domestic relationships, Estonia, international relationships, multi-stakeholder model, 2007 cyber-attacks, United States, whole-of-country

¹ Photo by ThisIsEngineering: <https://www.pexels.com/photo/code-projected-over-woman-3861969/>

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Cyberspace has emerged as a modern theater of conflict, driven by rapid technological advancement. As rival nations accelerate their digital capabilities, they increasingly threaten U.S. national security. To mitigate these risks, the United States must continue to innovate and reinforce its cyber defenses against evolving vulnerabilities. However, specifically within cyber diplomacy, the United States is behind.

The United States Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021 defines cyber diplomacy as “the policy to work internationally to promote an open, interoperable, reliable, unfettered, and secure Internet governed by the multi-stakeholder model, which promotes human rights, democracy, and rule of law, including freedom of expression, innovation, communication, and economic prosperity; and respects privacy and guards against deception, fraud, and theft.”²

Cyber diplomacy is a different way for the United States to use diplomatic measures to improve counterintelligence. For instance, Estonia, among other nations, has found a more effective approach to implementing cyber diplomacy through a whole-of-country approach. Unlike Estonia’s approach, the United States overemphasizes foreign partnerships, ignoring domestic relationships, and does not implement the vision outlined by the Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021. Nonetheless, the United States would benefit from a holistic approach that addresses these problems, similar to Estonia’s approach.

This paper is divided into multiple sections to address the nuanced aspects of cyber diplomacy. There will be these four sections: understanding cyber diplomacy, importance of cyber diplomacy, consequences of early policy decisions, and implications and outlook. This paper will provide the background information of cyber diplomacy within Estonia and the United States, why it is important for the United States to have a better cyber diplomacy system, why

² “H.R.1251,” Congress, April 22, 2021, https://www.congress.gov/117/bills/hr1251/BILLS_117hr1251rfs.pdf, 8.

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the United States' current cyber diplomacy system does not work, and how the United States could implement Estonia's whole-of-country approach.

Understanding Cyber Diplomacy

To understand how cyber diplomacy is practiced on the global stage, this segment examines the U.S. definition and contrasts it with Estonia's approach. The analysis is divided into two parts: one focused on American strategies, and the other on Estonian perspectives.

Estonian Cyber Diplomacy

Estonia has a more comprehensive approach to cyber diplomacy, leveraging both domestic and international actors. Estonia created a Cyber Diplomacy Department, led by an ambassador at Large in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.³ Estonia's department structure demonstrates a commitment to an efficient and involved cyber diplomacy approach.

Estonia's Cyber Diplomacy Department is involved in multilateral efforts. Most prominently, Estonia created the NATO Cooperative Cyber Defense Centre of Excellence (CCDCOE) in Estonia, which largely focuses on the Tallinn Manual, a resource that applies international law to cybersecurity.⁴ Similar to other nations around the world, such as the United States Estonia's commitment to international relations underscores the importance of this in cyber diplomacy policy. Differing from the United States, Estonia values involving multiple types of actors. Though this is part of a different department in Estonia, the following example

³ "Cyber Diplomacy," Republic of Estonia Ministry of Foreign Affairs, accessed July 1, 2025, <https://vm.ee/en/activity/digital-and-cyber-diplomacy/overview-cyber-diplomacy>.

⁴ "Cyber Capabilities and National Power Volume 2," International Institute for Strategic Studies, September 7, 2023, https://www.iiss.org/globalassets/media-library---content--migration/files/research-papers/2023/09/cyber-capabilities-and-national-power-vol-2/cyber-capabilities-and-national-power_volume-2.pdf, 42.

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describes one aspect of Estonia's whole-of-country approach. Estonia established the Cyber Defense Unit, a volunteer department of individuals from the private sector who help with cyber defense conflicts.⁵ Employing these individuals allows Estonia to gain greater insight from multiple sectors. These volunteers have perspectives that differ from their colleagues who work in the government. Consequently, they could solve problems in different ways, bringing a wide range of approaches to the Cyber Defense Unit. This cultivates an innovative environment that focuses on finding the best way to solve problems based on the knowledge and skills available across all sectors of Estonia.

United States Cyber Diplomacy

In 2022, the United States formed the Bureau of Cyberspace and Digital Policy (CDP), led by an Ambassador-at-Large under the State Department.⁶ This change allowed the United States to consolidate various departments' cyber diplomacy efforts because many other departments used to share this responsibility to reduce redundancy.⁷ This system ensures that there is greater efficiency for performing tasks since one unit, rather than multiple, participates in cyber diplomacy, and the roles are more defined.

The United States' approach to cyber diplomacy appears vastly different from Estonia's because the United States prioritizes strengthening relationships with other countries over using the resources within the United States. However, this differs from the multi-stakeholder model

⁵ FP Analytics, "Lessons from Estonia's Whole-of-Society Approach to Cyber Defense - Digital Front Lines," Digital Front Lines, September 6, 2023, <https://digitalfrontlines.io/2023/08/31/lessons-from-estonias-whole-of-society-approach-to-cyber-defense/>.

⁶ "Cyber Diplomacy: State's Efforts Aim to Support Us ...," Government Accountability Office, January 2024, <https://www.gao.gov/assets/d24105563.pdf>, 2.

⁷ See Note 2 Above

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that was directed by Congress when establishing the definition of cyber diplomacy. The Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021 was created to enhance America's cyber diplomacy efforts through establishing the foundation of the system by, for instance, creating the CDP.⁸ To achieve the multi-stakeholder model, the Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021 further explains that the government will use outside actors, such as private companies and non-governmental organizations.⁹ This act recognized using other actors as a way to implement the multi-stakeholder model. This multi stakeholder model is comparable to the whole-of-country approach due to both of their involvements of actors from multiple sectors. Contrary to the directive of this act, the CDP is guided by the goals to "build coalitions of countries that share U.S. strategic objectives to (1) counter threats to the U.S. digital ecosystem and (2) reinforce global norms of responsible state behavior."¹⁰ These broad goals mainly highlight that the CDP has a focus on counterintelligence through fostering relationships abroad, which is only one aspect of the multistakeholder model.

The United States' reports on its cyber diplomacy show that its activities are more in line with the CDP's goals, rather than the implementation method of the Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021. This has been done through the United States partnering with other countries or international organizations. For instance, in 2022, the CDP helped Denmark with its Copenhagen Pledge on Tech for Democracy, which has actors from across the world sign a pledge, committing to

⁸ "H.R.1251."

⁹ "H.R.1251," 8-9.

¹⁰ "Cyber Diplomacy: The Bureau of Cyberspace and Digital Policy's Efforts to Advance U.S. Interests," Government Accountability Office, April 29, 2025, https://files.gao.gov/reports/GAO_25-108445/index.html?_gl=1%2Ar6djd1%2A_ga%2AMTQwNDE3MTA4MC4xNzQ5NjY5OTg2%2A_ga_V393SNS3SR%2AczE3NTAwODg1NDUkbzmkZzEkdDE3NTAwODk0NzEkajYwJGwwJGgw.

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countering digital authoritarianism.¹¹ The CDP has also been involved in other organizations, such as a United Nations initiative on ensuring responsible state behavior in cyberspace.¹² These are just two examples of the CDP collaborating with other countries to advance its cybersecurity. These activities are important because they foster a global environment and understanding of respecting each country's cyberspace. This environment would not be possible without taking strides towards unity.

While international relationships play a key role in cybersecurity, a multifaceted approach to cyber diplomacy is essential for broader insight. In the United States, various government entities contribute to this effort, such as the CDP, which collaborates with agencies like the Department of Commerce to deepen subject-matter expertise.¹³ This interagency coordination supports innovation through the exchange of ideas and shared learning. However, critical gaps remain, particularly the limited involvement of the private sector and civilian stakeholders.

Overall, the United States lacks the comprehensive approach of Estonia's cyber diplomacy efforts. Though both countries support strengthening partnerships with other countries and international organizations, the only other action the CDP takes involves other government actors. This limits the CDP's ability to hear from professionals with different backgrounds, which is the largest benefit from a whole-of-country approach. Cyber diplomacy is a powerful tool that provides countries with a platform to build resilience and prevent cyber threats. To fully appreciate

¹¹ See Note 5 Above

¹² "Cyber Diplomacy: State's Efforts Aim to Support Us ...," 10.

¹³ "Cyber Diplomacy: The Bureau of Cyberspace and Digital Policy's Efforts to Advance U.S. Interests."

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its potential, it is important to understand its growing global significance.

Importance of Cyber Diplomacy

A strong cyber diplomacy strategy is increasingly vital in today's interconnected world. By examining its global relevance and the impact of external threats, this section highlights why the United States must strengthen and adapt its approach.

Cyber diplomacy is another way for countries to build partnerships within their own systems and beyond it to strengthen their defenses and global norms. Currently, the lack of international law and accountability for cyber-attacks poses a large issue for cyber diplomacy departments.¹⁴ Without clear expectations, it becomes challenging for countries to engage in meaningful dialogue and cooperation on shared security priorities. Luckily, the lead prosecutor of the International Criminal Court announced in 2023 that they will investigate and punish those responsible for cybercrimes using international law that has already been established for the first time.¹⁵ The International Criminal Court further developed its policies on cyberwar crimes through creating a draft policy in March 2025 that addresses accountability measures.¹⁶ This initiative taken by the International Criminal Court recognizes the need for global norms due to an increase in cyberattacks. Additionally, this highlights the world's reliance on cyber diplomacy. Cyber diplomacy efforts have led to advocating for international standards to ensure that there are

¹⁴ Andy Greenberg, "The International Criminal Court Will Now Prosecute Cyberwar Crimes," *Wired*, September 7, 2023, <https://www.wired.com/story/icc-cyberwar-crimes/>.

¹⁵ See Note 12 Above

¹⁶ "ICC Office of the Prosecutor Launches Public Consultation on Policy on Cyber-Enabled Crimes under the Rome Statute," International Criminal Court, March 7, 2025, <https://www.icc.cpi.int/news/icc-office-prosecutor-launches-public-consultation-policy-cyber-enabled-crimes-under-rome>.

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laws and consequences for cybercrimes through demonstrating a united front on issues, similar to the Copenhagen Pledge on Tech for Democracy. Cyber diplomacy is a necessary avenue that brings people together to create a peaceful cyber community.

To reach a peaceful cyber community, it involves more than creating consequences for cyber-attacks. The United States must anticipate these attacks to prevent them. China is a growing global threat to the United States due to its large economy and dedication to gathering intelligence on countries. The Chinese Communist Party performs espionage missions through a whole-of-country approach to gather intelligence on businesses, our government, military, and research institutions.¹⁷ One of the United States' largest adversaries is leveraging every resource it has to attack multiple sectors, not just the government. The United States is not utilizing every resource it could, which is hindering its ability and causing it to fall behind in its strategy. The best way to catch up is by meeting China where it is but through different methods. This will be explored in the outlook section of this paper.

Given the threat of China gathering intelligence on every sector, a whole-of-country approach is also better for creating innovative ideas. Each sector has had to or will have to learn how to counter these threats and defend itself since China is gathering intelligence on every sector, even beyond the government. The ideas and methods for defending oneself may vary, so having a whole-of-country approach could lead to more effective solutions for cyber issues.

The United States has vulnerabilities in its cyber diplomacy policy that could be exposed by countries such as China. Cyber diplomacy is an important tool that enables human interaction to transform norms and defense, such as in the International Criminal Court. This vulnerability is

¹⁷ Calder Walton and Greg Levesque, "An All-of-Society Approach to US Counterintelligence," The Cipher Brief, December 13, 2024, https://www.thecipherbrief.com/column_article/an-all-of-society-approach-to-us-counterintelligence.

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not new. The United States' shortcomings in cyber diplomacy can be traced back to earlier policy choices.

Consequences of Early Policy Decisions

Past policy decisions shaped how the CDP operates today, particularly its emphasis on international partnerships. While these choices helped establish a global network, they also led to missed opportunities to engage domestic talent and expertise. This section examines the key policies that contributed to the CDP's heavy reliance on relationships outside the United States.

One of the United States' earlier policies regarding cyberspace setup goals that led to a pattern for policymakers. According to the United States' 2011 International Strategy for Cyberspace, "the 2011 strategy ties global stability to the establishment of norms by like-minded states. Toward this end, the strategy calls on the United States to (1) engage in urgent dialogue to build consensus around principles of responsible behavior in cyberspace; (2) build international understanding around cyberspace norms, beginning with like-minded countries in bilateral dialogues; (3) carry this agenda into international organizations; (4) deter malicious actors from violating these norms; and (5) facilitate cyber security capacity-building."¹⁸ Regardless of the focus of the strategy, whether it is on domestic or international affairs, the United States focuses on its connections by leveraging capabilities within the government. This policy is similar to the United States' current cyber diplomacy policy of leveraging foreign relations to structure a world of America's desire. Though this has worked for America's foreign policy, this is not the same type of space that involves interacting with people. Instead, cyberspace is a battle fought online. Because the phenomena of relationships are deeply embedded in policies, the approach of the United States has not changed. However, the world has changed and evolved.

¹⁸ Emily O. Goldman, "From Reaction to Action: Adopting a Competitive Posture in Cyber Diplomacy," Texas National Security Review, 2020, <https://tnsr.org/2020/09/from-reaction-to-action-adopting-a-competitive-posture-in-cyber-diplomacy/>.

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The United States' inability to evolve can be seen in the CDP's focus on developing its relationships as part of its strategic goals. In 2024, the Government Accountability Office even admitted that the CDP's activities are found under the National Cybersecurity Strategy's pillar of creating international partnerships.¹⁹ The United States lacks a defined strategic goal that would allow the country to reach its goals of creating a multi-stakeholder model. This began with policies, such as the United States' 2011 International Strategy for Cyberspace, that created the groundwork for the CDP and other national security groups.

The foundation of these policies and ideology cannot be changed. Nevertheless, the concern becomes determining how to systematically move the United States towards a whole-of-country approach when there are barriers that outline different approaches to strategy. First, this begins with an understanding of what could occur if the United States does not adopt a whole-of-country approach.

Implications and Outlook

The threats that the United States face do not end with China. There are countless other countries or organizations that are involved in creating plans to harm the United States. It is time for the country to evaluate its current cyber diplomacy approach and evolve to a whole-of-country approach. This section is divided into two subsections: implications and outlook. Implications will discuss the consequences of not adopting an adequate strategy and why other countries' whole-of-government approach has worked for them. In the outlook subsection, the paper will outline the ways that the United States can implement a whole-of-country strategy.

Implications

¹⁹ "Cyber Diplomacy: State's Efforts Aim to Support Us ...," 8.

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First, it is important to understand what is at stake if the United States does not adopt a whole-of-country approach. This can be seen through cyber-attacks that occurred in Estonia in 2007. Estonia was not always a leader in cyber diplomacy, especially in 2007. During that time, Estonia fell victim to a cyber-attack that lasted 22 days after leaders moved a Soviet-era monument.²⁰ Russian hackers performed DDoS attacks, also known as Distributed Denial of Service attacks, which make servers work slower or not at all.²¹ These attacks made it difficult for Estonians to access and perform job duties for anything on the internet, such as banking, news channels, and public services.²² According to Lauri Almann, the permanent undersecretary of the Estonian defense ministry at the time of the attacks, the biggest scare for civilians occurred when the largest bank in Estonia, Swedbank, was attacked.²³ She further explained that if the attack was successful, it could have led to civil unrest due to a large number of people not being able to access their bank accounts.²⁴ The occurrence of these attacks demonstrates that any country could become the victim of a cyber-attack, whether or not they have the necessary defenses. Similar to many countries, Estonia had invested in its defenses and taken precautions, yet this country was

²⁰ Rain Ottis, Analysis of the 2007 cyber-attacks against Estonia from ..., accessed July 2, 2025, https://ccdcoe.org/uploads/2018/10/Ottis2008_AnalysisOf2007FromTheInformationWarfarePerspective.pdf, 1.

²¹ Adiningtyas Dwiputri Samsorizal, Eri Radityawara Hidayat, and Achmed Sukendro, "Analytical Study of Indonesian Cybersecurity: Lesson Learned from Estonian Cyberattacks In 2007," *International Journal of Arts and Social Science* 5, no. 2 (February 2022), <https://doi.org/https://www.ijassjournal.com/2022/V5I2/414659927.pdf>, 3.

²² Samsorizal et al, 2.

²³ "Turning around the 2007 Cyber Attack: Lessons from Estonia," *Estonian World*, September 17, 2024, <https://estonianworld.com/security/turning-around-2007-cyber-attack-lessons-estonia/>.

²⁴ See Note 21 Above

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still attacked. Not only this, but an attack of this caliber affects every person, even if they do not work in the government.

To mitigate these attacks during 2007, Estonia had to think creatively and try an approach that it had not before. To do this, “‘It was effectively an Internet kill switch for the country, nothing that a private sector company could have done on its own,’ says Almann, who believes that public-private sector cooperation helped deflect the attack in a matter of hours, not days or even weeks.”²⁵ Lauri Allman’s depiction of the attacks underscores the importance of having multiple perspectives when dealing with these attacks. Additionally, the indication she gave on the private sector recognizes the limitations that private companies have during these attacks, such as shutting down the internet. The public sector also faces limitations. The government would not have been able to link and deal with the attacks without a cooperation agreement that was signed between Estonia and Swedbank.²⁶ Nonetheless, this necessary cooperation led to the creation of the Cyber Defense Unit, so tech experts can work together to prevent future attacks.

The United States has never faced an attack of this caliber, but if it did, it would feel the effects as deeply as Estonia. These attacks had such a large effect on Estonia due to the country’s dependence on the internet. In the 1990s, Estonia launched e-Estonia, a government initiative that provides citizens with access to services online, including access to bank accounts online, declaring taxes online, and voting in elections.²⁷ Today, the United States is even more dependent on the internet for services than Estonia was in 2007, meaning that the effects of a large cyber-attack could hurt citizens and the government even more. The stakes have been raised to accommodate the world’s increased reliance on technology. Businesses and governments alike are

²⁵ See Note 21 Above

²⁶ See Note 21 Above

²⁷ “Story - e-Estonia,” e-Estonia, n.d., <https://e-estonia.com/story/>.

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under pressure. Adversaries, such as China, are attempting to gain intelligence on the United States' innovations. Adversaries are searching for any vulnerability to exploit. Therefore, it is imperative that the United States takes preventative measures to avoid attacks.

In another instance, Denmark adopted a whole-of-country approach, and the United States is involved in it. In 2021, Denmark began its Tech for Democracy initiative, which involved actors from corporations, organizations, and countries to discuss the protection of human rights and democracy in a new, technological era.²⁸ The report for Tech for Democracy revealed “Tech for Democracy established novel collaborations, produced knowledge and evidence, built principles of democratic technological development and use, and provided inputs to important international political, regulatory, and normative processes.”²⁹

Whole-of-country initiatives, such as Tech for Democracy and the Cyber Defense Unit, are effective because they empower people from diverse sectors to act. These initiatives provide platforms for all voices and ideas to be heard. Cyberattacks affect many industries and can look different for each. For the United States to protect each of these industries within the country, the United States must listen to the ideas, needs, and fears of each person. Collaborative environments foster innovation and could lead the United States to better ideas that the country would have never considered before.

Outlook

For the United States to adopt a whole-of-country approach, the government must involve citizens from the corporate, academic, military, and non-profit sectors to have a well-

²⁸ Adam Moe Fejerskov, Trine Rosengren Pejstrup, and Alma Tjalve, “Tech for Democracy,” DIIS, May 17, 2023, <https://www.diis.dk/en/research/tech-democracy>.

²⁹ See Note 18 Above

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rounded approach. To achieve this, the first step would be creating clear and defined goals and strategies for the CDP. Although the multi-stakeholder model is mentioned as a tool for implementation in the States Cyber Diplomacy Act of 2021, there is no mention of this model within the listed goals and strategies of the CDP. These strategies would include employing people from diverse backgrounds or, as Estonia did, establishing a volunteer defense unit. Changing these strategies would shift the department's focus to include more individuals in the planning process, in addition to the main objective of forming relationships.

Changing the goals would be the first step towards a whole-of-country approach, but to do this, one would need to convince the CDP and government of its importance. The government must understand the short-term and long-term benefits of a whole-of-country approach. The long-term benefits have already been defined throughout this paper as the future prevention of cyber-attacks. On the other hand, the short-term benefits address the hiring issue that the CDP faces. State Department officials have mentioned that the CDP is having problems hiring and training new staff members to meet the growth plans of the department.³⁰ If part of the staff were members of organizations, such as corporations or researchers, they would be aware of or have experienced cyber-attacks. These individuals would likely be easier to train based on their backgrounds and the necessary skills that are already developed.

The last issue faced in implementing a whole-of-country approach into the CDP would be incentivizing individuals from these varying sectors. The largest incentive would be money, but most individuals coming from research or corporate sectors would take a pay cut to work in a government job. Since money would not work, the next best way would be a more hands-on recruitment method. The CDP would need to target individuals who are retired and looking to

³⁰ “Cyber Diplomacy: The Bureau of Cyberspace and Digital Policy’s Efforts to Advance U.S. Interests.”

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make a difference at the end of their careers. Additionally, the CDP could try to recruit individuals who are not satisfied with their current job and are looking for a change towards careers that have a large emphasis on protecting the nation.

Conclusion

Adopting a whole-of-country approach is a necessary step that the United States must take towards preventing and strategically anticipating cyberattacks. The world has evolved, so the practices used must also evolve in this digital age. The United States has put too large an emphasis on relationships for its strategy. Cultivating partnerships should be part of the United States' strategy, but it should not be the only part. Additionally, the United States has emphasized the importance of a multi-stakeholder model, but the country has not implemented this in its goals. Estonia has successfully implemented a whole-of-country approach, which has led it to become a safer society with more innovative ideas. The United States can follow Estonia's lead by changing the CDP's goals and policies and hiring individuals from other sectors. The time to act is now. Failure to act could lead to devastating consequences, such as the cyber-attacks Estonia faced in 2007. Only through a whole-of-country approach can the United States secure its digital future and become a leader in global cyber diplomacy.

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